

Updating Fe VII energy levels for CHIANTI 10.1

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Kramida et al. (2022, ApJ) provided a new set of experimental energies for Fe VII. In this document I describe how these were integrated into the existing CHIANTI model of the ion (distributed with version 10.0).

I group together levels below and consider the new and/or revised energies that are proposed. Energies that are within a few cm^{-1} and have the same identification as the existing CHIANTI model I accept without checking.

To check a new energy, I consider the CHIANTI branching fractions (mostly from Li18) and look at the new wavelengths measured by K22 (in their Table 4) to see if the strongest transitions are being measured.

In the cases where the Kramida energy is rejected, this does not necessarily mean that a mistake had been made by these authors, but that the existing CHIANTI energy makes better sense in relation to the predicted line intensities. It may be that improved collision or structure calculations in the future may lead to be better agreement with the Kramida identifications.

Where level indices are given, these are always the indices in the CHIANTI 10.0 model of Fe VII.

Key

K22	Kramida et al. (2022, ApJ)
Li18	Li et al. (2018, MNRAS)
E81	Ekberg (1981, Phys. Scripta)
YL09	Young & Landi (2009, ApJ)
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3d3 quintet levels, indices 14-29 (389000-425000 cm^{-1})

There were only small adjustments to the existing CHIANTI energies and these were accepted.

K22 provided one new level energy for 5G2 (level 30). The K22 A-values give the strongest line at 235.809 (1-30), but the Li18 A-values give 4-30 at 245.937. It is this line that identified by K22 using the LY09 spectrum (not identified by YL09). I accept this identification.

The comparison of the level 30 energy with the Li18 theoretical energy is consistent with the other quintet levels. I have updated the theoretical energies of the other 5G levels using the observed-theoretical difference for 5G2.

4p levels, indices 31-36 (425000-434000 cm^{-1})

The six levels all previously had observed energies. Levels 33 and 35 have been modified as shown below. The original energies are from E81.

Level	CHIANTI	Previous	K22	Comment
3D3	33	430948	431608.5	Old energy assigned to (2G) 3G3 [47]
3F3	35	431609.5	432359.9	New

K22 find these two levels to be strongly mixed.

Level 33 has the strongest decay to level 3 in the CHIANTI model, with other decays to level 2 (13%) and level 7 (13%). K22 list all of these lines, but the decay to level 2 has the strongest intensity. They also list the long wavelength decay to level 12, which is expected from CHIANTI. I accept this identification.

Level 35 has the strongest decay to level 2 in the CHIANTI model, with further decays to levels 1 (13%), level 3 (29%) and level 12 (3%). All of these lines are listed by K22, although the decay to level 3 is the strongest. I accept this identification.

3d3 levels, indices 37-39 (418000-425000 cm⁻¹)

None of these levels were previously observed, but K22 provided energies for 38 and 39.

Level 38 ((b 2D) 3D2) decays to level 11 (4s 3D2) and K22 identified this line at 1256.246 Å in their lab spectrum. The decays to levels 2 and 4 were also measured at 236 and 246 Å. The Li18 A-values predict the decays to levels 6 and 7 are strongest, yet these weren't measured by K22. Also there should have been a stronger long wavelength line at 1237.8 Å that wasn't measured. *I reject this identification.*

Level 39 ((2G) 3F3) has the strongest decay to level 2, and this line is identified in the K22 lab spectrum. They also identify the decays to level 11 and level 1, which are the next strongest decays (although only 3% of the strongest line). I add this identification to CHIANTI.

3d3 and 4p levels, indices 40-46 (436000-440000 cm⁻¹)

The previous CHIANTI model had four observed energies. K22 provided new energies for the remaining levels.

Level 42 ((b2D) 3D3) has the strongest decay to level 3, and the next is to level 7 (19%). Both lines are reported by K22. They also give the decay to level 12, although this a little weaker than the decay to level 11, which is not reported. I add this identification to CHIANTI.

Level 43 ((2G) 3F4) has the strongest decay to level 3, with a weak decay (1.5%) to level 2. Both lines are measured by K22. They also measure the long wavelength line to level 12 at 1270.14 Å. I add this identification to CHIANTI.

Level 45 ((b2D) 3D1) has the strongest decay to level 6, with two other strong decays to levels 1 (67%) and 7 (70%). All three lines are measured by K22. The strongest of the long wavelength lines is to level 10 at 1146.90 Å, and this is also reported. I add this identification to CHIANTI.

3d3 levels, indices 47-52 (430000-432000 cm⁻¹)

None of these levels had observed energies in the previous CHIANTI model, but K22 assigned energies to five of the levels.

Level 47 ((2G) 3G3) has the strongest decay to level 1, with all others being weak (< 5%). K22 measure this line, but their strongest transition is to level 3, followed by level 7. *I reject this identification.*

Level 48 ((2P) 3P2) has the strongest decay to level 7, with other decays to level 4 (3%), level 6 (32%) and level 12 (7%). The latter is outside the K22 wavelength range, but decays to 10 and 11 are listed. K22 list the decay to level 7, but the level 6 decay is not listed. The decay to level 2 (very weak in CHIANTI) is very strong in K22. This level is very highly mixed, and 3P2 is only a minor component (see K22). *I reject this identification.*

Level 49 ((2P) 3P1) has the strongest decay to level 4, with additional decays to levels 5 (55%), 6 (35%), 7 (29%) and 9 (19%). K22 only list the decay to level 1, which is very weak in CHIANTI. *I reject this identification.*

Level 51 ((2G) 3G4) has the strongest decay to level 2, with additional decays to levels 3 (1%) and 8 (2%). There's also a very weak decay to level 12 (0.2%). K22 list all four lines, although the level 3 decay is stronger than the level 2 decay. Despite this, I accept the identification.

Level 52 ((2G) 3G5) has the strongest decay to level 3, with another weak decay (0.8%) to level 8. Both lines are reported by K22, and the level 3 transition is strongest. I accept the identification.

3d3 levels, indices 55-58 (440000-447000 cm⁻¹)

None of these levels had observed energies in the previous CHIANTI model. K22 provided observed energies for levels 55, 57, and 58.

Level 55 ((2G) 1G4) has two decays, the strongest to level 8 and the other to level 2 (43%). Both lines are listed by K22 and the intensities are consistent. I accept this identification.

Level 57 ((2G) 3H5) has two decays, the strongest to level 3 and the other to level 8 (68%). Both lines are listed by K22 and the intensities are consistent. I accept this identification.

Level 58 ((2P) 3D3) has a strong decay to level 7, with further decays to levels 3 (5%), level 4 (12%). K22 list the decays to levels 7 and 4, and the intensities are consistent with CHIANTI. I accept this identification.

3d3 levels, indices 59-75 (450000-455000 cm⁻¹)

None of these levels had observed energies in the CHIANTI model, and no updates are provided by K22.

However, K22 have a different parent term for the 3F levels (60, 66 and 71). CHIANTI has (2F) while K22 have (b 2D). I am changing the CHIANTI parent term to the K22 one.

3d3 levels, indices 76 to 84 (460000-465000 cm⁻¹)

None of these levels had observed energies in the CHIANTI model, but K22 provided energies for levels 76, 80, 81 and 84.

Level 76 ((4F) 3G3) has the strongest decay to level 4, with further decays to levels 1 (14%), 2 (9%) and 7 (8%). All four lines are listed by K22 (one is blended), and the strongest is the decay to level 4. I accept this identification.

Level 80 ((4F) 3G4) has the strongest decay to level 2 with further decays to levels 3 (85%) and 8 (1%). The decays to levels 2 and 3 are both listed by K22, although the level 3 decay is significantly stronger. Despite this, I accept this identification.

Level 81 ((4F) 3G5) has only two decays: the strongest to level 3 and the other to level 8 (92%). Both are listed by K22 and the intensities are reasonable. I accept this identification.

Level 84 ((b 2D) 1F3) has the strongest decay to level 4, and the only other significant decay to level 7 (8%). K22 only list the decay to level 4. The energy is very close to the Li18 theoretical energy (32 cm⁻¹) so I accept this identification, but with reservations.

3d3 levels, indices 92 to 101 (465000-485000 cm⁻¹)

The CHIANTI model had three observed energies (levels 92, 98 and 101), but all of these have significant changes in the K22 compilation. K22 also provide new energies for levels 94 and 95.

Level 92 ((2G) 1H5) has been given the energy 472560, compared to 464034 previously. The latter has been assigned to (4F) 3G5 (index 81). This makes sense when comparing with the Li18 theoretical energies. The CHIANTI model gives the strongest transition to level 8, with the only other significant transition to level 3 (8%). The measured line to level 3 is stronger than that to level 8. Despite this, I keep this identification.

Level 94 ((b 2D) 3F4) has the strongest decay to level 2, and another strong decay to level 3 (90%). There are also two weak decays to levels 8 (1.1%) and 12 (1.3%). K22 give the parent term as (2F). K22 identify the decays to levels 2 and 3, although the latter is weaker than expected. I keep this identification, and update the parent term.

Level 95 ((b 2D) 3F3) has the strongest decay to level 1, with other decays to levels 2 (27%), 3 (9%), and 4 (27%). K22 only identify the decay to level 1. However the 3F4-3F3 energy difference of 3899 is close to the Li18 separation of 4059, and the K22 intensity is comparable to the 2-94 transition (CHIANTI predicts they should have about the same intensity). I keep this identification and update the parent term.

Level 98 ((2F) 3G5) has been given the energy 478720 by K22 compared to 472559 in the CHIANTI model. The latter energy has been assigned to level 92 (see above). The strongest decay is to level 3, and the next strongest is to level 8 (2%). Both lines are listed by K22, although the weaker is blended with Fe VIII. The K22 energy is only 600 cm⁻¹ from the Li18 theoretical energy. I keep this identification.

Level 101 ((2F) 3G4) has the strongest decay to level 2, and additional decays to level 3 (11%) and level 8 (1%). K22 identify all three of these decays, and the intensities are about right. The Li18 theoretical energies for 3G5 (see above) and 3G4 are very close, and the new experimental energies are also very close. I accept this identification.

3d3 levels, index 112 (540000 cm⁻¹)

This level ((a 2D) 1D2) energy came from E81 originally, but this identification was rejected by K22. The main decay is to level 4, and the E81 line of 192.00 Å is actually due to Fe VIII. K22 suggested the line may be at 191.59 Å, but could not confirm this. The observed energy for this level has been removed from the CHIANTI model.

4d levels, indices 117-125 (550000-560000 cm⁻¹)

All of these levels had observed energies in the CHIANTI model. K22 swapped the energies for levels 119 and 123. Note that these levels mostly decay to 4p and 3d3 levels, hence their lines are found at longer wavelengths.

Level 119 (3D3) has the strongest decay to level 33 (4p 3D3), with other decays to level 28 (4p 1D2, 33%), level 42 (3d3 3D3, 25%) and level 44 (4p 3P2, 39%). K22 give two decays: to 4p 3F2 and 4p 3D3. They are about the same intensity, but the former is a blend.

Level 123 (3G3) has the strongest decay to level 34 (4p 3F2), with other decays to levels 37 (3d3 3F2, 52%) and 38 (3d3 3D2, 14%). Five lines are listed by K22, but they're all weak. The decay to level 34 is the strongest (as expected). The next two strongest decays are not listed.

Neither of these identifications are convincing, but they do correctly give the strongest transition from each level. I accept these identifications.

3d3 levels, indices 126-128 (550000-555000 cm⁻¹)

Two of the three levels of this 3D term had previously been assigned experimental energies; K22 assigned an energy for the third level.

Level 126 ((2F) 3D1) has the strongest decay to level 5, with further decays to levels 1 (60%) and 6 (67%). K22 list lines for all three of these decays. The level 6 decay is blended with Fe VI, but the intensities of the other two lines are consistent with the CHIANTI A-values. The energy separation of 3D1 & 3D2 is also reasonably close to the theoretical separation. I accept this identification.

3d3, 4p levels, indices 136-140 (550000-575000 cm⁻¹)

K22 assigned an energy to level 138, which previously didn't have one. Also level 136 had a parent term of b 2D in CHIANTI, but K22 has 2F (I updated this in the CHIANTI file).

Level 138 ((4P) 3P0) has only a single significant decay to level 6 in the CHIANTI model. This transition is listed by K22, but as a blend with Fe VI. However, K22 reported that the line is mostly due to Fe VI. I accept this identification.

3d3, indices 141-142 (570000 cm⁻¹)

K22 swapped the observed energies for these two levels.

Level 141 ((4P) 3P2) has the strongest decay to level 1, and weaker decays to levels 2 (7%), 4 (5%), 6 (17%) and 7 (47%). All five transitions are listed by K22. The level 1 decay is the strongest, as expected. The level 7 decay is much weaker than expected. The level decay is blended with the 7-142 decay discussed next. I accept this identification.

Level 142 ((4F) 3F2) has the strongest decay to level 1, with weaker decays to levels 2 (9%), 4 (2%), 6 (11%) and 7 (59%). Four of the transitions are listed by K22 (the level 4 decay is missing). The decay to level 1 is weaker than expected. CHIANTI predicts the 1-141 and 1-142 transitions to be about the same strength, but the K22 intensity for 1-142 is about a factor 10 lower. The 7-142 intensity is very strong, and it seems this is explained by K22's much larger A-value compared to CHIANTI. I accept this identification, but with some reservations.

3d3, 4f, indices 155-161 (630000-665000 cm⁻¹)

K22 have four new observed energies.

Level 156 ((a 2D) 1F3) has the strongest decay to level 8, with a weak decay to level 4 (4%). K22 only list a decay to level 3, which has a very low A-value. *I reject this identification.* K22

have a different parent term for this level (2F), which is consistent with Li18. I have made this change.

Level 157 (4f 3H4) has the strongest decay to level 8, with other decays to levels 2 (38%) and 123 (4d 3G3, 69%). K22 only list the latter transition. Note that the 3H line measurements come from Faulkner et al. (2001), which are fairly low resolution. *I reject this identification.*

Level 158 (4f 3H5) has the strongest decay to level 124 (4d 3G4), with other decays to levels 3 (93%) and 8 (85%). K22 only list the decay to level 124. *I reject this identification.*

Level 159 (4f3H6) only has the decay to level 125 (4d 3G5) in the CHIANTI model. K22 have this transition. *I reject this identification.*

3d3, 4f, indices 162-165 (660000-665000 cm⁻¹)

All of these four levels had observed energies in the CHIANTI model, and K22 swapped the energies for levels 162 and 165.

Level 162 (4f 3F4) has the strongest decay to level 3, with further decays to levels 2 (31%) and 8 (31%). K22 listed the decays to levels 3 and 8, with the latter being significantly stronger.

Level 164 (4f 1G4) has the strongest decay to level 8, with a further decay to level 3 (12%). K22 list both of these decays, plus the decay to level 2, which is very weak in CHIANTI (0.1%).

Checking the intensities of the four transitions listed by K22 against the current CHIANTI model, there is good agreement except for CHIANTI's 8-165 transition (158.167 Å) for which the K22 intensity is much too strong. This can't be fixed by swapping the observed energies for levels 162 and 165. *I therefore reject the revised identifications of K22 for levels 162 and 165.* The K22 A-values are significantly different to those currently in CHIANTI (from Tayal in this case), so it may be that an improved structure calculation would lead to agreement with K22.